

1 **Contrasting diversity patterns using Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures**
2 **deployed in pelagic vs. benthic environments**

3
4 Ernesto Villarino^{1*}, Anders Lanzen^{1,2}, Naiara Rodriguez-Ezpeleta¹, Iñaki Mendibil¹,
5 Angel Borja¹, Iñigo Muxika¹, Xabier Irigoien³, Joxe Mikel Garmendia¹ and Guillem
6 Chust¹

- 7
8 1. AZTI Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA),
9 Txatxarramendi Ugarte a z/g, 48395 Sukarrieta, Spain
10 2. IKERBASQUE – Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain
11 3. Ocean Science and Solutions Applied Research Institute (OSSARI), Education,
12 Research, and Innovation (ERI) Sector, NEOM, Tabuk, Saudi Arabia

13
14 Corresponding author: evillarino@azti.es

15
16 **Keywords:** ARMS, beta diversity, benthic, pelagic, ecology, dispersal.

17
18 **Running title:** comparing diversity pattern using pelagic and benthic ARMS

19
20 **ABSTRACT**

21 Efforts on the development of data-driven standardized sampling tools to monitor marine
22 benthic communities remain elusive, despite playing critical roles in biogeochemical
23 cycling, trophic transfer, and climate regulation. Here, we present a new application to
24 characterize benthic spatial biodiversity patterns and track the larval dispersal of benthic
25 species from nearshore coast to the pelagic environment combining DNA metabarcoding
26 and imagery on Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) deployed in both
27 pelagic and nearshore benthic systems across the Bay of Biscay's Basque Coast. Results
28 reveal a remarkably lower biodiversity in pelagic relative to benthic ARMS and a clear
29 spatial patterning showing well-defined clusters in benthic community composition with
30 the pelagic ARMS greatly differing to the benthic ones according both to metabarcoding
31 (ANOSIM $R = 0.82$; $p = 0.002$) and image analysis (ANOSIM $R = 0.87$; $p = 0.001$). We
32 also show that a large portion of the observed benthic community inhabiting the pelagic
33 domain (83.5%) probably originates from benthic habitats, while the benthic community

34 shared across pelagic and benthic habitats is considerably lower (24.9%). Further, we also
35 identified which benthic species successfully use the pelagic environment as
36 “steppingstone” to disperse across the ocean from nearshore coast, and found that the
37 unique benthic taxa inhabiting the pelagic ARMS consist of organisms with typically
38 larger dispersal distances relative to strictly sessile taxa with direct larvae development
39 found only in rock-attached benthic ARMS. Overall, these findings suggest that the
40 benthic system acts as population source delivering species towards a less diverse pelagic
41 domain. Taken together, this novel application of ARMS deployed in pelagic systems has
42 the potential to identify the often overlooked yet critically important benthic community
43 structure, as well as to unveil how dispersal pathways across benthic and pelagic habitats
44 can shape biodiversity patterns of coastal ecosystems.

45
46

INTRODUCTION

47

48 Benthic communities are key indicators of ocean health (Borja et al., 2000; Teixeira et
49 al., 2009) playing important roles in trophic transfer (Griffiths et al., 2017), nutrient
50 cycling (Ehrnsten et al., 2020; Pawlik & McMurray, 2020), and climate regulation
51 (Krause-Jensen & Duarte, 2016; Ramesh et al., 2015). They also support key ecosystem
52 services (Costanza et al., 1997; Snelgrove, 1999) and provide shelter and food to many
53 ecologically relevant functional groups, including fish or seaweed (Krause-Jensen &
54 Duarte, 2016; Kritzer et al., 2016; Seitz et al., 2014). These functions largely depend on
55 the distribution of the species that make up the benthic ecosystems (Henseler et al., 2019),
56 an extremely diverse environment largely affected by human pressures in a changing
57 ocean (Doney et al., 2011; Duarte, 2014; Halpern et al., 2008; Levin & Dayton, 2009).
58 Efforts on the development of data-driven standardized monitoring tools are therefore
59 essential, if we are to assess how levels of marine biodiversity are maintained or
60 compromised by anthropogenic activities in nearshore ecosystems (Danovaro et al., 2016;
61 Muxika et al., 2007; Teixeira et al., 2009), and comply the European directives (Water
62 Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive) to achieve Good
63 Environmental Status (Borja et al., 2013) in these systems.

64

65 There is a lack of standardized methodologies for monitoring and assessing the ecological
66 status of rocky systems (Obst et al., 2020), where most of biodiversity is cryptic (Pearman
67 et al., 2016). The Coral Reef Ecosystem Division (CRED) of the United States National

68 Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) developed the Autonomous Reef
69 Monitoring Structures (ARMS) (Zimmerman & Martin, 2004) in an attempt to
70 standardize the sampling of benthic habitats and assess their biodiversity across habitats
71 and regions. Designed to mimic the 3D structural complexity of coral reef environments
72 (Plaisance et al., 2011; Ransome et al., 2017), but with applications also in temperate and
73 polar rocky habitats across the Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea (David et al., 2019; Obst
74 et al., 2020; Pearman et al., 2020; Pennesi & Danovaro, 2017). ARMS are composed of
75 stacked nested PVC plates acting as biological stations allowing mobile and sessile
76 organisms to settle and shelter within. ARMS-associated communities can be analyzed
77 either morphologically, inferred from photographs (David et al., 2019), or through DNA
78 metabarcoding (Carvalho et al., 2019; Leray & Knowlton, 2015; Pearman et al., 2019;
79 Pearman et al., 2020) or combining both (Cahill et al., 2018; Duarte et al., 2023; Kelly et
80 al., 2017; Pearman et al., 2016). Photo-analysis techniques can be considered a relatively
81 fast and cost-effective first order community screening tool (David et al., 2019; Goñi et
82 al., 2017; Kornder et al., 2021). DNA metabarcoding approaches allow a broader
83 biodiversity spectrum to be identified, as benthic systems often comprise small sessile,
84 encrusting, or mobile organism – the so called cryptobiome – difficult to spot in
85 traditional surveys (Carvalho et al., 2019; Leray & Knowlton, 2015; Pearman et al.,
86 2020). Nevertheless, both photo-analysis and DNA based methods applied to
87 standardized sampling of ARMS (Leray & Knowlton, 2015) have proven complementary
88 to document changes in the diversity of marine life across spatial, environmental, or
89 temporal gradients (Duarte et al., 2023; Kelly et al., 2017; Kopp et al., 2023; Obst et al.,
90 2020; Steyaert et al., 2022).

91

92 Most benthic species dwell in habitat patches connected by the passive transport of larvae
93 during the planktonic phase, before they settle in as sedentary adults. Dispersal of benthic
94 species and the resulting connectivity, or lack thereof, between habitats will therefore
95 determine the probability of migration (MacArthur & Wilson, 1967) and the resulting
96 spatial patterns of biodiversity (Mouquet & Loreau, 2003). However, difficulties
97 associated with tracking the trajectory and fate of propagules and larvae have limited our
98 knowledge of dispersal strategies and population connectivity of many marine species
99 (Cowen, 2007). Further, changes in species composition among sites, or beta diversity
100 (Whittaker, 1960), is not only determined by dispersal, but also by niche processes
101 (Hutchinson, 1957), which assemble species best adapted to local environmental

102 conditions. Both dispersal and niche processes interact to drive a decline in community
103 similarity over increasing geographical distance, commonly called the distance-decay
104 relationship (Nekola & White, 1999). Recent ARMS studies looking at cryptobenthic
105 diversity and distance-decay patterns across European Seas suggest that distance between
106 sampling sites, combined with environmental differences, were key factors driving spatial
107 distribution of benthic communities (Pearman et al., 2019; Pearman et al., 2020; Pearman
108 et al., 2018; Steyaert et al., 2022). However, no studies have compared diversity patterns
109 across depth using ARMS deployed both in benthic and pelagic environments, which can
110 be relevant to unveil complex dispersal pathways and connectivity of marine
111 communities in coastal systems.

112

113 Here, we present a new application of ARMS deployed in the benthic environment across
114 the southern Bay of Biscay's Basque Coast. We compared benthic biodiversity patterns
115 using ARMS deployed in a pelagic environment (offshore longlines at 5 and 15 m depth,
116 35 – 45 m above the bottom) with ARMS deployed in rock-attached benthic
117 habitats. Specifically, we aim to detect those benthic species that do recruit in the pelagic
118 environment during their larval phase, and quantify the portion of the benthic community
119 that successfully use the pelagic environment as “steppingstone” to disperse from
120 nearshore coast. To do so, we combined photo-analysis and metabarcoding techniques on
121 benthic ARMS deployed in the surface and seafloor over four sampling sites across the
122 Basque Coast (Mendexa, Lekeitio, Zumaia, Pasaia). We expect a relatively higher
123 diversity in the benthic ARMS attached to the rock compared to the ARMS in the pelagic
124 environment, as benthic environments tend to be more heterogenous implying a greater
125 niche partitioning due to competition (Chesson, 2000), and because benthic species
126 typically have narrow distributions and less chance to reach pelagic sites from the coast
127 (Hubbell, 2001). We also hypothesize that ARMS in pelagic environments will represent
128 a subset of the community present at rock-attached benthic ARMS, but would harbor a
129 higher number of dispersing-larvae benthic species relative to benthic ARMS on rock,
130 where non-dispersing larvae species should dominate (Chust et al., 2016). This novel
131 benthic ARMS application deployed in pelagic environments might potentially provide
132 new insights on how nearshore benthic communities are spatially structured, and how
133 ocean connectivity and transport pathways determine benthic larvae dispersal throughout
134 pelagic environment.

135

METHODS

136

137 *1. ARMS deployment and study areas*

138

139 Each ARMS unit consists of nine 22.5×22.5 cm PVC plates stacked on top of a 35×45
140 cm base plate with spacers separating the plates and bars on alternate levels creating flow
141 fields. Further details on the standard assembly, deployment and recovery of the ARMS
142 are available on <https://naturalhistory.si.edu/research/global-arms-program>. Here, we
143 compared biodiversity patterns of benthic species in ARMS deployed in pelagic and
144 benthic habitats (Mendexa, Lekeitio, Zumaia, and Pasaia) across the southern Bay of
145 Biscay's Basque Coast in two periods: 2013-2014 and 2018-2019 (**Fig. 1a**). Specifically,
146 ARMS in pelagic habitats were deployed in Mendexa and benthic ARMS were placed in
147 Lekeitio, Zumaia and Pasaia. The distance between the ARMS in pelagic habitat to
148 nearest coast is 2 km, while the distance between the ARMS in pelagic habitat to closest
149 rock-attached benthic ARMS (Lekeitio) is 5 km, approximately. The Basque Coast is
150 characterized by the dominance of the rocky substrate, with cliffs and abrasion platforms
151 interspersed with sandy beaches (Borja et al., 2004). It is a very exposed coast to
152 prevailing waves, with estuaries largely affected by human pressures (Cearreta et al.,
153 2004) (**Fig. 1a**).

154

155 ARMS in pelagic habitats were deployed by divers in Mendexa on May 6th, 2018. Six
156 ARMS were attached to offshore longlines (seafloor at 50 m depth), placed in pairs
157 hanging from the same rope at 5 m and 15 m in three different areas (**Fig. 1a-b**). ARMS
158 were collected on June 6th, 2019. Due to technical issues and stormy weather, only two
159 ARMS were left out of the six deployed: ARMS-1: at 5 m and ARMS-2: at 5 m. The
160 latter fell to 30 m depth for the last four months and to bottom (50 m) for the last two
161 weeks, therefore only ARMS-1 was used in the analysis (**Fig. 1a-b**).

162

163 Rock-attached benthic ARMS were deployed at seafloor in Lekeitio, Zumaia, and Pasaia,
164 which are separated by 20-50 km, between May 2013 and June 2014 (Pearman et al.,
165 2020) (**Fig. 1a-b**). Three replicates were taken at each location, separated by 5–10 m;
166 ARMS were deployed at a depth ranging from 10 to 12 m. Macroalgae covered rock is
167 the predominant substrate the ARMS were deployed on (**Fig. 1a-b**).

168

169 Both ARMS in pelagic habitats and rock-attached benthic ARMS were recovered and
170 returned to the laboratory after being submerged for 12-14 months (**Fig. 1b**), where they
171 were dismantled and processed. Each plate surface was gently brushed to separate the
172 bigger mobile fauna (>2000 μm), without detaching sessile organisms. Plates were kept
173 in seawater aerated with bubblers before being processed with photo-analysis and
174 metabarcoding techniques.

175

176 *2. Identification of the biological community*

177

178 *2.1 Photo-analysis*

179

180 Top (T) and bottom (B) surfaces were analyzed on three selected plates (P1, P4, and P8,
181 from top to bottom) at each ARMS, following David et al. (2019) (**Fig. 2**). Top and
182 bottom faces represent different environmental conditions for the organisms: The top
183 surface of plate 1 (P1T) is exposed to light without any protection from predators, in
184 contrast to the other five faces. Among the shaded plate-faces, P1B, P4T, P8T are open
185 to currents, while the flow through in P4B and P8B is more limited (**Fig. 2**).

186

187 Each plate-face was photographed using a DSLR Nikon D70 with an aspherical 28-70
188 mm f/2.8 Sigma EX lens at a focal length of approximately 44 mm. The camera was set
189 facing down horizontally at approximately 0.5 m from the plates, which were placed in
190 white trays. The ISO was set at 200 and the aperture of the diaphragm was fixed at f/10
191 (with variable shutter speed depending on the lighting for each photograph). The
192 photographs were taken in RAW and high-quality large JPG formats. The RAW files
193 corresponding to the selected plates were processed in Darktable 2.6.2: (1) white balance
194 using the tray as a reference; (2) lens corrections using predefined profiles; (3) alignment
195 and perspective correction; and (4) basic settings (tuning of exposure, blacks, highlights,
196 midtones, saturation and vibrance). Processed images were saved as TIFF files.

197

198 Photographs were analyzed using stratified random point count methodology, i.e.
199 dividing each photograph in 64 squares and randomly overlying one point within each
200 square (Trygonis & Sini, 2012). Then the organisms or features covered by each point
201 were identified (in the case of organisms, to the lowest possible taxonomic level). For the
202 analysis of photographs corresponding to the ARMS collected in 2014 Photoquad®
203 software was used, whereas Coral Point Count with Excel (CPCe) was used for the

204 photographs from the ARMS collected in 2019 (Kohler & Gill, 2006). The outputs from
205 both software provide relative abundance or cover values as well as diversity indices of
206 the species found at each plate which is later used for subsequent statistical analysis. In
207 this study, relative cover (%) occupied by the sessile organism at each plate was used.
208 Therefore, for each site we included 6 samples in the analysis (two faces and three plates).
209 **(Fig. 2).**

210

211 *2.2 Metabarcoding*

212

213 *2.2.1 DNA extraction and COI metabarcoding*

214

215 The processing and metabarcoding data analysis of the rock-attached benthic ARMS
216 analysed here have been previously described in Pearman et al. (2020), and ARMS in the
217 pelagic habitat were processed in the same manner. Briefly, ARMS were disassembled
218 while submerged in water obtained from the sampling sites. Sessile and mobile (<2000
219 μm) organisms growing on the plates were scraped off and homogenized using a blender
220 (approximately 40 g of tissue), and preserved in Ethanol 96%. The water containing the
221 ARMS was then filtered through a stack of sieves (2000 μm , 500 μm and 106 μm). For
222 both benthic and pelagic ARMS, DNA from the sessile fraction was extracted by
223 homogenizing the bulk sample scraped from the plates, while DNA from the mobile
224 fractions included the three size fractions within the crushed bulk mobile organisms (2000
225 μm , 500 μm and 106 μm). DNA extraction, amplification of the mitochondrial
226 Cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI), and library preparation followed a similar protocol
227 as described in (Pearman et al., 2020). Briefly, 10g of blended material was used for DNA
228 extraction using the kit DNeasy PowerMax Soil Kit (QIAGEN). Approximately 10 ng of
229 DNA was amplified from all resulting DNA extracts as well as a negative control in
230 triplicates using primers F-5'GGWACWGGWTGAACWGTWTAYCCYCC-3' and R-
231 5'TAIACYTCIGGRTGICCRAARAAAYCA'3 with the PCR profile 98°C for 3min,
232 followed by 27 cycles at 98°C for 10 s, 46°C for 45 s and, 72°C for 45 s, with a final
233 extension of 5 min at 72°C(Geller et al., 2013; Leray et al., 2013). Resulting PCR products
234 (pooling triplicates) were cleaned using Ampure XP beads (BECKMAN), and a second
235 round of amplification (eight PCR cycles) was performed following the Illumina 16S
236 Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation Nextera cotags, followed by a second
237 clean-up. Normalized amounts of each library-based Qubit 2.0 quantification were pooled

238 and sequenced using an Illumina MiSeq platform with v3 chemistry and paired 300 bp
239 read length.

240

241 2.2.2 Amplicon Sequence Variant inference and taxonomic assignments

242

243 Raw metabarcoding read data was subjected to read pair overlapping, filtering and
244 determination combining the data described in Pearman et al. (2020) (available from the
245 INDSC Sequence Read Archive with Bioproject accession PRJNA479721) and the data
246 derived for this study (Bioproject accession RJEB63262). Read overlapping, filtering and
247 identification of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) was carried out as described
248 previously in (Lanzén et al., 2021). Briefly, reads were merged using *vsearch* v2.21.1
249 accepting up to 40 mismatches (Rognes et al., 2016) and thereafter primer and linker
250 sequences were removed using *cutadapt* v2.8 (Martin, 2011), discarding any merged
251 sequences that did not contain the full primer sequence with or which contained more
252 than two mismatches. Thereafter, all amplicon sequences shorter than 274 bp or longer
253 than 333 bp were discarded. ASV determination was then carried out using SWARM
254 v2.2.1 (Mahé et al., 2015) using default settings, followed by removal of singletons,
255 reference-based and then *de novo* filtering of likely chimeric OTUs, using *vsearch*, with
256 the Midori v248 + DARN reference database, available through CREST v4 (Lanzén et
257 al., 2012) (<https://github.com/xapple/crest4>). Finally, post-clustering correction were
258 carried out using LULU (Frøslev et al., 2017) with a 90% similarity cutoff, and taxonomic
259 assignments using CREST (Lanzén et al., 2012).

260

261 All ASVs not classified as Metazoa, to class rank or better, were removed. We also
262 removed clear non-marine SVs classified as Insecta (56 ASVs) and Arachnida (16 ASVs).
263 Any remaining likely contaminants, based on comparative abundance between samples
264 and negative controls, were identified and removed using *decontam* (Davis et al., 2018)(3
265 ASVs).

266

267 In this analysis, the relative abundance mean (relative number of reads) of the three
268 replicates for each site was used. Subsequently, we grouped the fractions separating the
269 sessile from the mobile assemblages (>2000 µm, 500-1000 µm and 90-500 µm) at each
270 site. To compensate for uneven sequencing depth between samples, only ASVs with an
271 abundance of 0.1% in at least one sample were kept.

272 3. Statistical analysis

273

274 3.1 Local diversity patterns

275

276 To summarize the structure and richness of the benthic communities alpha diversity
277 metrics were used. Alpha diversity statistics were analysed with one way ANOVA and
278 tested for significant differences for the factor site and size in metabarcoding, and the
279 factor site and plate face in photo-analysis. ANOVAs were performed on Linear Mixed
280 Models using the *lme* package in R. This generic function fits a linear mixed-effects
281 model in the formulation described in (Laird & Ware, 1982) but allowing for nested
282 random effects. The within-group errors are allowed to be correlated and/or have unequal
283 variances. Explanatory variables habitat, site, size, plate face and trait (mobile vs. sessile)
284 were used as fixed effect for each model. Shapiro test for normality in species or ASV
285 richness and homogeneity of variance in residuals were performed prior to ANOVA.

286

287 3.2 Community dissimilarity patterns across sites

288

289 The ANalysis Of SIMilarity (ANOSIM) test was used to analyse if the samples were
290 more similar within than across sites (Mendexa-pelagic, Lekeitio, Zumaia and Pasaia),
291 size fractions (>2000 μm , 500-1000 μm and 90-500 μm), plate face (Top and Bottom),
292 habitat (pelagic and benthic) and plate number (P1, P4, P8). In brief, ANOSIM provides
293 a way to test statistically whether there is a significant difference between two or more
294 groups of sampling units. The ANOSIM statistic “R” compares the mean of ranked
295 dissimilarities between groups (between sites, for example) to the mean of ranked
296 dissimilarities within groups (within sites, for example). An R value close to 1 suggests
297 dissimilarity between groups while an R value close to 0 suggests an even distribution of
298 high and low ranks within and between groups. R values below 0 suggest that
299 dissimilarities are greater within groups than between groups. Hence, the higher the R
300 value, the more dissimilar the sites are in terms of benthic community composition. The
301 significance of the R statistic is determined by permuting across the groups and
302 comparing the position of the observed R value to the null distribution.

303

304 Community dissimilarity on Bray-Curtis distances between sites, size fractions and plate
305 faces was also analysed using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) with the
306 function *metaMDS* in *vegan* (Oksanen et al., 2013). Local Contribution to Beta Diversity

307 (LCBD) (Legendre & De Cáceres, 2013) was calculated with *adespatial* (Dray et al.,
308 2018) and was used to describe the degree of uniqueness of each habitat and to assess its
309 contribution to the total variation in benthic community composition. Total diversity was
310 calculated on a Hellinger transformed community matrix. Beta diversity was partitioned
311 computing the sum of squares of a sampling unit or habitats as a proportion of the total
312 diversity (Legendre & De Cáceres, 2013).

313

314 We also undertook a habitat specific analysis to identify taxa with significantly higher
315 abundances in ARMS deployed in pelagic system vs. rock-attached benthic ARMS, and
316 to quantify the taxa that were habitat specific. This analysis was only undertaken in the
317 metabarcoding dataset due to the low sampling size in the photo-analysis dataset. To do
318 so, we first collapsed ASVs to phylotypes representing the same taxonomic classifications
319 within each habitat, and then phylotype abundances were compared between pelagic and
320 benthic habitats using a one-sided Student's t-test (function *t.test*).

321

322 RESULTS

322

323 1. Community composition and local biodiversity patterns

324

325 Metabarcoding of the pelagic samples resulted in 171142 sequence reads (13022 – 56138
326 per sample). Together with the 201286 sequence previously described reads from benthic
327 samples (Pearman et al. 2020) we obtained 556 ASVs after quality filtering based on
328 taxonomy and abundance.

329

330 In metabarcoding, Arthropoda, Cnidaria, Mollusca and, to a lesser extent, Annelida
331 dominated the composition of ARMS in pelagic habitats across all size classes (**Fig. 3a-**
332 **b**). The rock-attached benthic ARMS showed similar phyla dominance to the ARMS in
333 pelagic habitats, but the relative portion of each phylum was more even, and Annelida's
334 contribution considerably increased while other groups including Chordata,
335 Echinodermata and Bryozoa emerged. In photo-analysis, similar taxa to metabarcoding
336 dominated the community composition in ARMS deployed in pelagic habitats, but
337 Porifera loomed and Cnidaria decreased, while in rock-attached benthic ARMS only
338 Bryozoa and Annelida appeared to drive the community (**Fig. 3c-d**).

339

340 Average ASV richness varied across habitats (pelagic vs. benthic), sites, size classes and
341 traits (mobile vs. sessile) in metabarcoding (**Fig. 4a**). Across sites, the ASV richness was
342 the highest in Zumaia (349 ASVs) and the lowest in the pelagic ARMS of Mendexa (158
343 ASVs) (**Fig. 4a, Fig. 4c**), where a significantly lower number of ASVs compared to all
344 other sites was found ($p = 0.044$; **Table 1**). Similarly, significant differences in ASV
345 richness were shown across size classes ($p = 0.015$; **Table 1**), with 90-500 μm being the
346 richest size fraction (481 ASV) and $>2000 \mu\text{m}$ the poorest (326 ASV) (**Fig. 4a, Fig. 4d**).
347 Across traits, mobile ASV showed greater richness (540 ASV) compared to sessile taxa
348 (365 ASV) (**Fig. 4a, Fig. 4i**), but differences were not significant ($p = 0.493$; **Table 1**).

349
350 In photo-analysis, no significant differences in species richness were observed across
351 habitats and plate faces, with very similar species richness within pelagic and benthic
352 habitats (17 and 18 species, respectively) ($p = 0.511$; **Table 1, Fig. 4b, Fig. 4h**) and within
353 top and bottom plate faces (23 species in both) ($p = 0.326$; **Table 1, Fig. 4b, Fig. 4g**).
354 However, across sites, significant differences in species richness were detected ($p =$
355 0.028 ; **Table 1**), with Mendexa harbouring the highest number of species (17 species)
356 and Lekeitio (9 species) the lowest (**Fig. 4b, Fig. 4f**). The patterns observed in photo-
357 analysis are limited by the low number of taxa identified at the species level. Figure 2 is
358 an example of a photograph representing different colonization degree of benthic
359 communities in benthic (left panel, a-d) and pelagic (right panel e-f) ARMS for Plate 1
360 and 8 at Top and Bottom faces. a) Top side of plate 1, b) Bottom side of plate 1, d) Top
361 side of plate 8, d) Bottom side of plate 8. e-f) same for pelagic ARMS. In a) a community
362 of brown algae (Phaeophyceae) can be appreciated, in contrast to b) where annelid worms
363 Serpulidae dominate. In c) and d) a colony of bryozoans (Cheilostomatida) is shown. In
364 pelagic ARMS, Serpulidae dominate the Bottom face of Plate 8 h) while in the other
365 Plates (e-f-g) a combination of algae, Bivalvia mollusks, barnacles and biofouling can be
366 seen.

367

368 2. Community dissimilarity patterns across sites

369

370 In both metabarcoding and photo-analysis, NMDS ordination analysis based on Bray-
371 Curtis dissimilarities revealed a clear spatial patterning showing well defined clusters in
372 community composition across sites and habitats, with the community assembly within
373 ARMS in pelagic habitat greatly differing to the other rock-attached benthic sites (**Fig.**

374 **5a-b**). Community dissimilarity patterns are shown in **Fig. 6a-d**. In metabarcoding,
375 highest benthic dissimilarities were observed between ARMS in pelagic habitats and
376 rock-attached benthic ARMS (**Fig. 6a**), however, dissimilarities were relatively high also
377 across benthic sites and size fractions (**Fig. 6a-b**). In photo-analysis, across benthic sites,
378 community dissimilarities were sensibly lower compared to metabarcoding, but “pelagic”
379 vs. “benthic” patterns were similar across plate face, sites, and plate number (**Fig. 6c-d**).

380

381 We also investigated whether the benthic community dissimilarity within habitats
382 differed from the dissimilarity between habitats. The same analysis was undertaken across
383 sites, size classes, and traits in metabarcoding, as well as plate number and plate face in
384 photo-analysis. The ANOSIM test revealed significantly lower dissimilarities within than
385 between habitats and sites, but not across size classes and traits in metabarcoding (**Fig.**
386 **7a-b-c**), or across plate face and plate number in photo-analysis (**Fig. 7c-d**). For
387 metabarcoding, rock-attached benthic ARMS dissimilarities were significantly higher to
388 ARMS in pelagic habitats (**Fig. 7b**), however, in photo-analysis the opposite was
389 observed (**Fig. 7e**). Hence, the habitat and site appear to be key driving benthic spatial
390 distribution within Basque Coast nearshore ecosystems, with contrasting results
391 according to the method used.

392

393 For both metabarcoding and photo-analysis, LCBD was the highest in “pelagic”-
394 compared to rock-attached benthic ARMS (**Fig. 8a-b**). This means a higher pool of
395 unique benthic species inhabiting those ARMS in pelagic habitats, probably species with
396 high dispersal capacities over their planktonic phase that can settle pelagic environments,
397 i.e., planktotrophic larvae development vs. lecithotrophic or direct development. In
398 metabarcoding, from a total of 556 ASVs present in ARMS in pelagic habitats and rock-
399 attached benthic ARMS, 4.7 % of ASVs were unique to pelagic habitats (26 ASVs), 71.6
400 % of ASVs were unique to benthic habitats (398 ASVs) and 23.7% of ASVs (132 ASVs)
401 were shared across habitats (**Table 2a, Fig. 8c**). In fact, the abundance-based analysis
402 across “benthic” and “pelagic” ASVs revealed quite high differences in some groups, i.e.,
403 cnidarians (*Muggiæa atlantica*, other hydroids i.e., *Plumularia*, or anemones i.e.,
404 *Aiptasiidae*), and amphipods (*Jassa slatteryi* and other Photid amphipods) (**Table 2b**).
405 However, 83.5 % of total “pelagic” ASVs were shared across pelagic and benthic habitats
406 (158 ASVs were present in the pelagic ARMS, and 132 ASVs were shared across

407 habitats) while 24.9 % of the total benthic ASVs were shared across habitats (530 ASVs
408 in benthic ARMS; 132 ASVs shared across habitats). (Table 2a, Fig. 8c).

409

DISCUSSION

410

411 There is a pressing need to preserve marine resources due to the complex array of threats
412 derived from anthropogenic activities (e.g., overfishing, pollution, ocean acidification and
413 warming, invasive species) (Halpern et al., 2019), which needs adequate monitoring. We
414 have presented a new application to monitor and characterize benthic biodiversity
415 patterns combining next generation sequencing and imagery on ARMS deployed in
416 pelagic systems. We found a relatively higher ASV richness in rock-attached benthic
417 ARMS relative to those deployed in pelagic habitats, perhaps explained by the typically
418 greater niche partitioning in benthic domains due to competition relative to shallower
419 systems (Chesson, 2000), but also due to the difficulty of benthic species to reach the
420 pelagic ocean from the coast (Hubbell, 2001).

421

422 Although community similarity is sensitive to the species richness of the corresponding
423 sites and habitats, the NMDS community analysis separated relatively well across pelagic
424 and benthic sites in both metabarcoding and imagery. Further, community assembly
425 patterns differed greatly across sites in both methods, consistent with previous efforts
426 across European Seas (Pearman et al., 2020). Photo-analysis identifies a lower number of
427 benthic species relative to metabarcoding, and perhaps it is not able to detect differences
428 in species richness across pelagic and benthic habitats, while metabarcoding does so.
429 Hence, the lower sampling size and broader taxonomic resolutions obtained from photo-
430 analysis relative to metabarcoding might explain the different patterns observed across
431 methods.

432

433 We consider the approach taken here to be a promising monitoring application and a
434 scalable method not only to assess status and change of ecological communities
435 regionally (Borja et al., 2013), but also to determine benthic larvae dispersal throughout
436 the pelagic environment. Benthic assemblages colonizing artificial units in rocky areas
437 have been found to show different colonization and succession patterns (Moura et al.,
438 2008). Here, a large portion of the benthic community inhabiting the pelagic ARMS
439 appeared to originate from nearby benthic habitats, probably a community dominated by

440 benthic species with dispersing larvae drifted by ocean currents until they settle in
441 (Lefebvre et al., 2003). This finding confirms our hypothesis that the “pelagic”
442 community can be considered a subset of the nearby benthic one, likely acting as source
443 population delivering species to the pelagic domain (MacArthur & Wilson, 1967). We
444 also show that the unique taxa found in ARMS in pelagic habitats consist of organisms
445 with typically larger dispersal distances, including Cnidaria and amphipods, relative to
446 strictly sessile taxa with direct larvae development found only in benthic ARMS (e.g.
447 *Eurydice* sp., *Gammaropsis* sp., *Thyasira* sp., etc.) (van der Linden et al., 2016). Another
448 interesting point supporting the dispersal capacity of benthic species to pelagic habitats
449 upon their larval phase is the relatively higher abundance of European flat oyster *Ostrea*
450 *edulis*, a typical supralittoral species, found in pelagic ARMS compared to benthic ones.
451 This finding is surely tied to different oyster aquaculture efforts undertaken in Mendexa
452 or Mutriku during 2016-2017 (Ortega et al., 2020; Zorita, 2020). Therefore, we speculate
453 that the significant differences in community dissimilarity found across benthic and
454 pelagic habitats may have arisen from those unique species found across habitats. The
455 lacking pattern observed in size and traits ruling community patterns might be linked to
456 the high number of dispersing larvae species found in both sessile and mobile taxa and
457 the low number of “pelagic” ARMS replicates, somehow blurring the analysis. However,
458 our results do partially support the trait-dispersal hypothesis where the non-dispersing
459 larvae show typically more narrow distributions relative dispersing larvae benthic taxa
460 (Chust et al., 2016).

461

462 We recognize several limitations on the methods used here to estimate regional patterns
463 of benthic diversity. The stormy weather and technical issues in the sampling reduced the
464 sampling size considerably in the ARMS deployed pelagic environments. On the other,
465 the identification at a specific level of many species by photography remains a challenge.
466 Further, photographs were taken from a top-down perspective; therefore, organisms with
467 the ability to grow over others are more likely to be seen, neglecting the 3D structure of
468 cryptobenthic communities (Kornder et al., 2021). Other caveats include the margin of
469 error of the use of metabarcoding, or the nature of the material of the ARMS that can be
470 a limiting factor only to species that recruit in this type of substrate, hence not
471 representing the whole biodiversity spectrum. Finally, rock-attached benthic ARMS and
472 ARMS in pelagic habitats were collected during different years (2013-2014 benthic,
473 2018-2019 pelagic), therefore temporal discrepancies across habitats and environmental

474 variables might have contributed to the difference in community composition for the
475 “site” and “habitat” factor in our statistical analyses. However, within the constraints of
476 the sampling and methodology, we consider that the small environmental change
477 observed over five years in the area (0.1 °C/decade in SST approx. (Chust et al., 2022))
478 is not strong enough for a community turnover, hence, biodiversity comparison across
479 habitats could be undertaken. We also consider that the application of ARMS in pelagic
480 environments can pave the way to describe biodiversity patterns across benthic and
481 pelagic habitats, and potentially determine species dispersal distances (Cowen, 2007;
482 Villarino et al., 2018) throughout pelagic environment. Addressing these challenges in
483 future monitoring programs will help to further elucidate the drivers of benthic
484 biodiversity change in coastal areas. For example, placing ARMS in several pelagic sites
485 to increase discriminatory power, deploying benthic and pelagic ARMS in the same sites
486 and years, and compiling contextual data of those sites, or deploying many pelagic ARMS
487 along transects to study dispersal scales (Azpeitia et al., 2016). In addition, other than
488 spatial patterns, we consider a need to move beyond episodic studies and build up time-
489 series of ARMS upon genetic and imagery to unveil how environmental changes over
490 time may affect benthic community assembly patterns.

491

492 In summary, we found clear spatial patterns in community structure across sites and
493 habitats within the Basque Coast rocky shore ecosystems, with the composition of ARMS
494 in pelagic habitat greatly differing to the rock-attached benthic ones, according to both
495 metabarcoding and image analysis. Our findings also confirms that the benthic system
496 acts as population source towards a less diverse pelagic domain, as seen in the large
497 proportion of the shared species across habitats in pelagic ARMS (83.3%) and the lower
498 proportion of species shared in benthic ARMS (24.9%). Further, the migration of the
499 species across the two habitats seems to be tied to dispersal traits (White, 2019), as the
500 unique taxa found in ARMS in pelagic habitats consist of organisms with typically larger
501 dispersal distances relative to strictly sessile taxa with direct larvae development found
502 only in rock-attached benthic ARMS. Overall, these findings highlight the use of ARMS
503 in pelagic habitats as a new application to expand the current understanding of the
504 ecological mechanisms and dispersal processes underlying distributional patterns of
505 benthic diversity in the nearshore ecosystems.

506

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

507

508 EV: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation,
509 Investigation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Methodology; AL: Formal analysis,
510 Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Data Curation. NRE: Writing – review &
511 editing, Methodology; IM: Methodology, AB: Writing – review & editing, Supervision,
512 Funding acquisition, Conceptualization; IMu: Writing – review & editing, Methodology;
513 JMG: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, XI: Writing – review & editing,
514 Conceptualization; GC: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition,
515 Conceptualization.

516

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

517

518 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
519 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

520

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

521

522 The metadata and code that support the findings of this study are openly available in
523 GitHub https://github.com/ErnestoVillarino/pelagic_benthic_ARMS. Raw sequence
524 generated in this study are available through the INSDC Sequence Read Archive (Bio
525 Project accession PRJEB63262).

526

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

527

528 This study has been supported by Urban Klima 2050 – LIFE 18 IPC 000001 funded by
529 the European Union’s LIFE and OBAMA NEXT HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01
530 (Grant Agreement 101081642). Anders Lanzén is further supported by a Research
531 Associate scholarship from IKERBASQUE (Basque Foundation for Science). We thank
532 laboratory technicians and at-sea sampling crew and divers from AZTI for their help. We
533 also thank Igor Granado and Gotzon Mandiola for technical help and Izaskun Zorita for
534 useful comments. This paper is contribution n° [to be filled in at acceptance] from AZTI,
535 Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance

REFERENCES

- Azpeitia, K., Ferrer, L., Revilla, M., Pagaldai, J., & Mendiola, D. (2016). Growth, biochemical profile, and fatty acid composition of mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lmk.) cultured in the open ocean of the Bay of Biscay (northern Spain). *Aquaculture*, 454, 95-108. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.12.022>
- Borja, A., Aguirrezabalaga, F., Martínez, J., Sola, J. C., García-Arberas, L., & Gorostiaga, J. M. (2004). Benthic communities, biogeography and resources management. *Oceanography and marine environment of the Basque Country*, 70(18), 455-492.
- Borja, A., Elliott, M., Andersen, J. H., Cardoso, A. C., Carstensen, J., Ferreira, J. G., Heiskanen, A.-S., Marques, J. C., Neto, J. M., Teixeira, H., Uusitalo, L., Uyarra, M. C., & Zampoukas, N. (2013). Good Environmental Status of marine ecosystems: What is it and how do we know when we have attained it? *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 76(1), 16-27. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2013.08.042>
- Borja, A., Franco, J., & Pérez, V. (2000). A marine biotic index to establish the ecological quality of soft-bottom benthos within European estuarine and coastal environments. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 40(12), 1100-1114.
- Cahill, A. E., Pearman, J. K., Borja, A., Carugati, L., Carvalho, S., Danovaro, R., Dashfield, S., David, R., Féral, J.-P., Olenin, S., Šiaulys, A., Somerfield, P. J., Trayanova, A., Uyarra, M. C., & Chenuil, A. (2018). A comparative analysis of metabarcoding and morphology-based identification of benthic communities across different regional seas. *Ecology and Evolution*, 8(17), 8908-8920. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.4283>
- Carvalho, S., Aylagas, E., Villalobos, R., Kattan, Y., Berumen, M., & Pearman, J. K. (2019). Beyond the visual: using metabarcoding to characterize the hidden reef cryptobiome. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 286(1896), 20182697. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.2697>
- Cearreta, A., Irabien, M. J., & Pascual, A. (2004). Human activities along the Basque coast during the last two centuries: geological perspective of recent anthropogenic impact on the coast and its environmental consequences. *Oceanography and marine environment of the Basque Country. Elsevier oceanography series*, 70, 27-50.
- Chesson, P. (2000). Mechanisms of Maintenance of Species Diversity. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 31, 343-366. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/221736>
- Chust, G., González, M., Fontán, A., Revilla, M., Alvarez, P., Santos, M., Cotano, U., Chifflet, M., Borja, A., Muxika, I., Sagarminaga, Y., Caballero, A., de Santiago, I., Epelde, I., Liria, P., Ibaibarriaga, L., Garnier, R., Franco, J., Villarino, E., . . . Uriarte, A. (2022). Climate regime shifts and biodiversity redistribution in the Bay of Biscay. *Science of The Total Environment*, 803, 149622-149622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2021.149622>
- Chust, G., Villarino, E., Chenuil, A., Irigoien, X., Bizsel, N., Bode, A., Broms, C., Claus, S., Fernández de Puelles, M. L., Fonda-Umani, S., Hoarau, G., Mazzocchi, M. G., Mozetič, P., Vandepitte, L., Veríssimo, H., Zervoudaki, S., & Borja, A. (2016). Dispersal similarly shapes both population genetics and community patterns in the marine realm. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 28730. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep28730>

- Costanza, R., d'Arge, R., de Groot, R., Farber, S., Grasso, M., Hannon, B., Limburg, K., Naeem, S., O'Neill, R. V., Paruelo, J., Raskin, R. G., Sutton, P., & van den Belt, M. (1997). The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature*, 387(6630), 253-260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/387253a0>
- Cowen, R. K., G. Gawarkiewicz, J. Pineda, S.R. Thorrold, and F.E. Werner. (2007). Population connectivity in marine systems: An overview. *Oceanography*, 20(3), 14-21. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2007.26>.
- Danovaro, R., Carugati, L., Berzano, M., Cahill, A. E., Carvalho, S., Chenuil, A., Corinaldesi, C., Cristina, S., David, R., Dell'Anno, A., Dzhenbekova, N., Garcés, E., Gasol, J. M., Goela, P., Féral, J.-P., Ferrera, I., Forster, R. M., Kurekin, A. A., Rastelli, E., . . . Borja, A. (2016). Implementing and Innovating Marine Monitoring Approaches for Assessing Marine Environmental Status [Review]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00213>
- David, R., Uyarra, M. C., Carvalho, S., Anlauf, H., Borja, A., Cahill, A. E., Carugati, L., Danovaro, R., De Jode, A., Feral, J. P., Guillemain, D., Martire, M. L., D'Avray, L. T. D. V., Pearman, J. K., & Chenuil, A. (2019). Lessons from photo analyses of Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures as tools to detect (bio-)geographical, spatial, and environmental effects. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 141(October 2018), 420-429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.02.066>
- Davis, N. M., Proctor, D., Holmes, S. P., Relman, D. A., & Callahan, B. J. (2018). Simple statistical identification and removal of contaminant sequences in marker-gene and metagenomics data. *Microbiome*, 6, 226.
- Doney, S. C., Ruckelshaus, M., Emmett Duffy, J., Barry, J. P., Chan, F., English, C. A., Galindo, H. M., Grebmeier, J. M., Hollowed, A. B., Knowlton, N., Polovina, J., Rabalais, N. N., Sydeman, W. J., & Talley, L. D. (2011). Climate Change Impacts on Marine Ecosystems. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 4(1), 11-37. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-041911-111611>
- Dray, S., Blanchet, G., Borcard, D., Guenard, G., Jombart, T., Larocque, G., Legendre, P., Madi, N., Wagner, H. H., & Dray, M. S. (2018). Package 'adespatial'. *R package*, 2018, 3-8.
- Duarte, C. M. (2014). Global change and the future ocean: a grand challenge for marine sciences [Specialty Grand Challenge]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00063>
- Duarte, S., Vieira, P. E., Leite, B. R., Teixeira, M. A. L., Neto, J. M., & Costa, F. O. (2023). Macrozoobenthos monitoring in Portuguese transitional waters in the scope of the water framework directive using morphology and DNA metabarcoding. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 281, 108207. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2022.108207>
- Ehrnsten, E., Sun, X., Humborg, C., Norkko, A., Savchuk, O. P., Slomp, C. P., Timmermann, K., & Gustafsson, B. G. (2020). Understanding Environmental Changes in Temperate Coastal Seas: Linking Models of Benthic Fauna to Carbon and Nutrient Fluxes [Review]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00450>
- Frøslev, T. G., Kjøller, R., Bruun, H. H., Ejrnæs, R., Brunbjerg, A. K., Pietroni, C., & Hansen, A. J. (2017). Algorithm for post-clustering curation of DNA amplicon data yields reliable biodiversity estimates. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 1188-.
- Geller, J., Meyer, C., Parker, M., & Hawk, H. (2013). Redesign of PCR primers for mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I for marine invertebrates and application in all-taxa biotic surveys. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 13(5), 851-861. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12138>

- Goñi, L. G., Borja, Á., & Uyarra, M. C. (2017). Investigación Marina.
- Griffiths, J. R., Kadin, M., Nascimento, F. J. A., Tاملander, T., Törnroos, A., Bonaglia, S., Bonsdorff, E., Brüchert, V., Gårdmark, A., Järnström, M., Kotta, J., Lindegren, M., Nordström, M. C., Norkko, A., Olsson, J., Weigel, B., Žydelis, R., Blenckner, T., Niiranen, S., & Winder, M. (2017). The importance of benthic–pelagic coupling for marine ecosystem functioning in a changing world. *Global Change Biology*, 23(6), 2179-2196. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13642>
- Halpern, B. S., Frazier, M., Afflerbach, J., Lowndes, J. S., Micheli, F., O'Hara, C., Scarborough, C., & Selkoe, K. A. (2019). Recent pace of change in human impact on the world's ocean. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 11609. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47201-9>
- Halpern, B. S., Walbridge, S., Selkoe, K. A., Kappel, C. V., Micheli, F., D'Agrosa, C., Bruno, J. F., Casey, K. S., Ebert, C., Fox, H. E., Fujita, R., Heinemann, D., Lenihan, H. S., Madin, E. M. P., Perry, M. T., Selig, E. R., Spalding, M., Steneck, R., & Watson, R. (2008). A Global Map of Human Impact on Marine Ecosystems. *Science*, 319(5865), 948-952. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1126/science.1149345>
- Henseler, C., Nordström, M. C., Törnroos, A., Snickars, M., Pecuchet, L., Lindegren, M., & Bonsdorff, E. (2019). Coastal habitats and their importance for the diversity of benthic communities: A species- and trait-based approach. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 226, 106272. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2019.106272>
- Hubbell, S. P. (2001). *The Unified Neutral Theory of Biodiversity and Biogeography (MPB-32)*. Princeton University Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt7rj8w>
- Hutchinson, G. E. (1957). Concluding Remarks. *Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative Biology*, 22, 415-427. <https://doi.org/10.1101/sqb.1957.022.01.039>
- Kelly, R. P., Closek, C. J., O'Donnell, J. L., Kralj, J. E., Shelton, A. O., & Samhour, J. F. (2017). Genetic and Manual Survey Methods Yield Different and Complementary Views of an Ecosystem [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00283>
- Kohler, K. E., & Gill, S. M. (2006). Coral Point Count with Excel extensions (CPCe): A Visual Basic program for the determination of coral and substrate coverage using random point count methodology. *Computers & Geosciences*, 32(9), 1259-1269. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2005.11.009>
- Kopp, D., Faillettaz, R., Le Joncour, A., Simon, J., Morandea, F., Le Bourdonnec, P., Bouché, L., & Méhault, S. (2023). Assessing without harvesting: Pros and cons of environmental DNA sampling and image analysis for marine biodiversity evaluation. *Marine Environmental Research*, 188, 106004. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2023.106004>
- Kornder, N. A., Cappelletto, J., Mueller, B., Zalm, M. J. L., Martinez, S. J., Vermeij, M. J. A., Huisman, J., & de Goeij, J. M. (2021). Implications of 2D versus 3D surveys to measure the abundance and composition of benthic coral reef communities. *Coral Reefs*, 40(4), 1137-1153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-021-02118-6>
- Krause-Jensen, D., & Duarte, C. M. (2016). Substantial role of macroalgae in marine carbon sequestration. *Nature Geoscience*, 9(10), 737-742. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2790>
- Kritzer, J. P., DeLucia, M.-B., Greene, E., Shumway, C., Topolski, M. F., Thomas-Blate, J., Chiarella, L. A., Davy, K. B., & Smith, K. (2016). The Importance of Benthic Habitats for Coastal Fisheries. *BioScience*, 66(4), 274-284. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biw014>

- Laird, N. M., & Ware, J. H. (1982). Random-effects models for longitudinal data. *Biometrics*, 38(4), 963-974.
- Lanzén, A., Dahlgren, T. G., Bagi, A., & Hestetun, J. T. (2021). Benthic eDNA metabarcoding provides accurate assessments of impact from oil extraction, and ecological insights. *Ecological Indicators*, 130, 108064. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01312-x>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1470160X21007299>
- Lanzén, A., Jørgensen, S. L., Huson, D. H., Gorfer, M., Grindhaug, S. H., Jonassen, I., Øvreås, L., & Urich, T. (2012). CREST – Classification Resources for Environmental Sequence Tags. *Plos One*, 7(11), e49334. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0049334>
- Lefebvre, A., Ellien, C., Davoult, D., Thiébaud, E., & Salomon, J. C. (2003). Pelagic dispersal of the brittle-star *Ophiothrix fragilis* larvae in a megatidal area (English Channel, France) examined using an advection/diffusion model. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 57(3), 421-433. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714\(02\)00371-2](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714(02)00371-2)
- Legendre, P., & De Cáceres, M. (2013). Beta diversity as the variance of community data: dissimilarity coefficients and partitioning. *Ecology Letters*, 16(8), 951-963. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12141>
- Leray, M., & Knowlton, N. (2015). DNA barcoding and metabarcoding of standardized samples reveal patterns of marine benthic diversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(7), 2076-2081. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.1424997112>
- Leray, M., Yang, J. Y., Meyer, C. P., Mills, S. C., Agudelo, N., Ranwez, V., Boehm, J. T., & Machida, R. J. (2013). A new versatile primer set targeting a short fragment of the mitochondrial COI region for metabarcoding metazoan diversity: application for characterizing coral reef fish gut contents. *Frontiers in Zoology*, 10(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-10-34>
- Levin, L. A., & Dayton, P. K. (2009). Ecological theory and continental margins: where shallow meets deep. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 24(11), 606-617. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.04.012>
- MacArthur, R. H., & Wilson, E. O. (1967). *The Theory of Island Biogeography*. Princeton University Press. <https://books.google.es/books?id=a10cdkywhVgC>
- Mahé, F., Rognes, T., Quince, C., de Vargas, C., & Dunthorn, M. (2015). Swarm v2: highly-scalable and high-resolution amplicon clustering. *PeerJ*, 3, e1420. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.1420>
- Martin, M. (2011). Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *EMBnet.journal*, 17(1), 10-12. <http://journal.embnet.org/index.php/embnetjournal/article/view/200>
- Mouquet, N., & Loreau, M. (2003). Community patterns in source-sink metacommunities. *Am Nat*, 162(5), 544-557. <https://doi.org/10.1086/378857>
- Moura, A., da Fonseca, L. C., Cúrdia, J., Carvalho, S., Boaventura, D., Cerqueira, M., Leitão, F., Santos, M. N., & Monteiro, C. C. (2008). Is surface orientation a determinant for colonisation patterns of vagile and sessile macrobenthos on artificial reefs? *Biofouling*, 24(5), 381-391. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927010802256414>
- Muxika, I., Borja, Á., & Bald, J. (2007). Using historical data, expert judgement and multivariate analysis in assessing reference conditions and benthic ecological status, according to the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution*

- <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2006.05.025>
- Nekola, J. C., & White, P. S. (1999). The distance decay of similarity in biogeography and ecology. *Journal of Biogeography*, 26(4), 867-878. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2699.1999.00305.x>
- Obst, M., Exter, K., Allcock, A. L., Arvanitidis, C., Axberg, A., Bustamante, M., Cancio, I., Carreira-Flores, D., Chatzinikolaou, E., Chatzigeorgiou, G., Christmas, N., Clark, M. S., Comtet, T., Dailianis, T., Davies, N., Deneudt, K., de Cerio, O. D., Fortič, A., Gerovasileiou, V., . . . Pavludi, C. (2020). A Marine Biodiversity Observation Network for Genetic Monitoring of Hard-Bottom Communities (ARMS-MBON). *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.572680>
- Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F. G., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., Minchin, P., O'hara, R., Simpson, G., Solymos, P., Stevens, M. H. H., & Wagner, H. (2013). Community ecology package. *R package version*, 2(0), 321-326.
- Ortega, A., Egiguren, L., Cruz, Z., Escuredo, P., Ferrer, L., Franco, J., Garcia, C., Garcia Muñoz, S., González, M., Ibarguen, Monica., Illanes, E., Izquierdo, X., Labriska, E., Lagos, LE., Larreta, J., Martin, P., Montoya, JA., Pardo, M., Picaza, N., Puertolas,, E., R., Marta., Rios, Y., Roca, S., & Santa Cruz, E., Solaun, O., Zorita, I. (2020). *Informe final MUSSELS: Caracterización del cultivo de mejillón en ZPM offshore de Euskadi (Mendexa) partiendo de captación de semilla natural y generación de estudios de viabilidad económica para productores.*
- Pawlik, J. R., & McMurray, S. E. (2020). The Emerging Ecological and Biogeochemical Importance of Sponges on Coral Reefs. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 12(1), 315-337. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010419-010807>
- Pearman, J. K., Anlauf, H., Irigoien, X., & Carvalho, S. (2016). Please mind the gap – Visual census and cryptic biodiversity assessment at central Red Sea coral reefs. *Marine Environmental Research*, 118, 20-30. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2016.04.011>
- Pearman, J. K., Aylagas, E., Voolstra, C. R., Anlauf, H., Villalobos, R., & Carvalho, S. (2019). Disentangling the complex microbial community of coral reefs using standardized Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS). *Molecular Ecology*, 28(15), 3496-3507. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15167>
- Pearman, J. K., Chust, G., Aylagas, E., Villarino, E., Watson, J. R., Chenuil, A., Borja, A., Cahill, A. E., Carugati, L., Danovaro, R., David, R., Irigoien, X., Mendibil, I., Moncheva, S., Rodríguez-Ezpeleta, N., Uyarra, M. C., & Carvalho, S. (2020). Pan-regional marine benthic cryptobiome biodiversity patterns revealed by metabarcoding Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures. *Molecular Ecology*, 29(24), 4882-4897. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15692>
- Pearman, J. K., Leray, M., Villalobos, R., Machida, R. J., Berumen, M. L., Knowlton, N., & Carvalho, S. (2018). Cross-shelf investigation of coral reef cryptic benthic organisms reveals diversity patterns of the hidden majority. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 8090. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-26332-5>
- Pennesi, C., & Danovaro, R. (2017). Assessing marine environmental status through microphytobenthos assemblages colonizing the Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) and their potential in coastal marine restoration. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 125(1), 56-65. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.08.001>

- Plaisance, L., Caley, M. J., Brainard, R. E., & Knowlton, N. (2011). The Diversity of Coral Reefs: What Are We Missing? *PLOS ONE*, 6(10), e25026. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0025026>
- Ramesh, R., Chen, Z., Cummins, V., Day, J., D'Elia, C., Dennison, B., Forbes, D. L., Glaeser, B., Glaser, M., Glavovic, B., Kremer, H., Lange, M., Larsen, J. N., Le Tissier, M., Newton, A., Pelling, M., Purvaja, R., & Wolanski, E. (2015). Land–Ocean Interactions in the Coastal Zone: Past, present & future. *Anthropocene*, 12, 85-98. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2016.01.005>
- Ransome, E., Geller, J. B., Timmers, M., Leray, M., Mahardini, A., Sembiring, A., Collins, A. G., & Meyer, C. P. (2017). The importance of standardization for biodiversity comparisons: A case study using autonomous reef monitoring structures (ARMS) and metabarcoding to measure cryptic diversity on Mo'orea coral reefs, French Polynesia. *PLOS ONE*, 12(4), e0175066. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175066>
- Rognes, T., Flouri, T., Nichols, B., Quince, C., & Mahé, F. (2016). VSEARCH: a versatile open source tool for metagenomics. *PeerJ*, 4, e2584. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2584>
- Seitz, R. D., Wennhage, H., Bergström, U., Lipcius, R. N., & Ysebaert, T. (2014). Ecological value of coastal habitats for commercially and ecologically important species. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 71(3), 648-665. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fst152>
- Snelgrove, P. V. R. (1999). Getting to the Bottom of Marine Biodiversity: Sedimentary Habitats: Ocean bottoms are the most widespread habitat on Earth and support high biodiversity and key ecosystem services. *BioScience*, 49(2), 129-138. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1313538>
- Steyaert, M., Lindhart, M., Khrizman, A., Dunbar, R. B., Bonsall, M. B., Mucciarone, D. A., Ransome, E., Santodomingo, N., Winslade, P., & Head, C. E. I. (2022). Remote reef cryptobenthic diversity: Integrating autonomous reef monitoring structures and in situ environmental parameters [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.932375>
- Teixeira, H., Neto, J. M., Patrício, J., Veríssimo, H., Pinto, R., Salas, F., & Marques, J. C. (2009). Quality assessment of benthic macroinvertebrates under the scope of WFD using BAT, the Benthic Assessment Tool. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 58(10), 1477-1486. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2009.06.006>
- Trygonis, V., & Sini, M. (2012). photoQuad: A dedicated seabed image processing software, and a comparative error analysis of four photoquadrat methods. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 424-425, 99-108. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2012.04.018>
- van der Linden, P., Borja, A., Rodríguez, J. G., Muxika, I., Galparsoro, I., Patrício, J., Veríssimo, H., & Marques, J. C. (2016). Spatial and temporal response of multiple trait-based indices to natural- and anthropogenic seafloor disturbance (effluents). *Ecological Indicators*, 69, 617-628. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.05.020>
- Villarino, E., Watson, J. R., Jönsson, B., Gasol, J. M., Salazar, G., Acinas, S. G., Estrada, M., Massana, R., Logares, R., Giner, C. R., Pernice, M. C., Olivar, M. P., Citores, L., Corell, J., Rodríguez-Ezpeleta, N., Acuña, J. L., Molina-Ramírez, A., González-Gordillo, J. I., Cózar, A., . . . Chust, G. (2018). Large-scale ocean connectivity and planktonic body size. *Nature Communications*, 9, 142-142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02535-8>

- White, J. W., M.H. Carr, J.E. Caselle, L. Washburn, C.B. Woodson, S.R. Palumbi, P.M. Carlson, R.R. Warner, B.A. Menge, J.A. Barth, C.A. Blanchette, P.T. Raimondi, and K. Milligan. (2019). Connectivity, dispersal, and recruitment: Connecting benthic communities and the coastal ocean. *Oceanography*, 33(3), 50-59.
- Whittaker, R. H. (1960). Vegetation of the Siskiyou Mountains, Oregon and California. *Ecological Monographs*, 30, 279-338.
- Zimmerman, T. L., & Martin, J. W. (2004). Artificial reef matrix structures (ARMS): an inexpensive and effective method for collecting coral reef-associated invertebrates. *Gulf and Caribbean Research*, 16(1), 59-64.
- Zorita, I., Puértolas, E., Solaun, O., Rodríguez, G., Muxika, I., Arantzamendi, L., Bald, J., Picaza, N., Labriska, E., Ríos, Y., García, S., Caro, M., Illanes, E., Álvarez, S., Santa Cruz, S., Hernando, MJ., Iwasaki, I and Roca, S. . (2020). *DESOS: Desarrollo y optimización industrial del cultivo de ostra*.

TABLES

Table 1. ANOVA and Linear Mixed models on ASVs richness across sites, size, habitat and traits for metabarcoding and on species richness across site and plate face for photo-analysis. Habitat: Pelagic, Benthic; Site: Mendexa-pelagic, Lekeitio, Zumaia, Pasaia; Size (μm): >2000, 500-1000, 90-500, Sessile; Trait: Mobile, Sessile; Plate face: Top face, Bottom face.

Method	Linear Mixed model					ANOVA (lme)	
	Model (random effect)	Level	df	t	p	F	p
Metabarcoding	Richness ~ Habitat (Site+Size)	Pelagic	1	-3.040	0.093	9.242	0.093
		Benthic		13.77	0		
	Richness ~ Site (Size+Habitat)	Mendexa	3	4.557	0	5.735	0.044*
		Lekeitio		3.029	0.029*		
		Zumaia		2.576	0.049*		
		Pasaia		4.109	0.009*		
	Richness ~ Size (Site+Habitat)	Sessile	3	5.779	0	5.990	0.015*
		>2000		-1.266	0.237		
		500-1000		1.110	0.295		
	Richness ~ Trait (Site+Habitat)	90-500		2.813	0.020*		
Mobile		1	7.355	0	0.493	0.493	
Sessile	-0.708		0.493				
Photo-analysis	Richness ~ Habitat (Site+Plate Face)	Pelagic	1	0.792	0.511	0.627	0.511
		Benthic		4.649	0		
	Richness ~ Site (Plate Face+Habitat)	Mendexa	3	9.840	0	3.796	0.028*
		Lekeitio		-2.545	0.020*		
		Zumaia		-1.866	0.078		
		Pasaia		0.356	0.726		
	Richness ~ Plate Face (Site+Habitat)	Bottom	1	8.086	0	1.015	0.326
Top		-1.007		0.326			

Table 2. Metabarcoding ARMS. a) Number of unique and shared ASVs across pelagic and benthic habitats b) Overrepresented taxa in pelagic ARMS relative to benthic ones, as well as a short description of the trophic style and dispersal traits of each taxa.

a)

Method	Total ASVs richness Pelagic and benthic	ASVs richness pelagic	ASVs richness benthic	ASVs richness unique pelagic	ASV richness unique benthic	ASV richness shared pelagic benthic
Metabarcoding	556	158	530	26	398	132

b)

Taxa	<i>p</i>	Pelagic sites abundance (%)	Benthic sites abundance (%)	Trophic style. Mobility / Pelagic type
Rhabditophora (spp.)	0.03	0.33	0.01	Flatworms, mostly parasitic. Carnivores. Mobile
<i>Diplosoma listerianum</i>	0.02	0.08	0	Colonial tunicates. Cosmopolitan. Filter feeders. Sessile with mobile larvae.
<i>Caprella</i>	0.04	0.25	0	Skeleton shrimps (amphipods). Mostly predatory omnivores but filter feeders exist. Benthic but mobile.
<i>Jassa</i>	0.04	5.79	0	Infralittoral benthic amphipod inhabiting self-constructed tubes in seagrass. Generally feeding on sessile hydroids. Benthic but mobile
Photidae	0.02	3.59	0.03	Family of amphipods. Benthic but mobile
<i>Doto</i>	0.02	1.25	0.08	Genus of nudibranchs. Generally feeding on sessile hydroids. Benthic but mobile
<i>Gammaropsis</i>	0.01	2.39	0	Genus of amphipods. Suspension feeder. Benthic but mobile
Hydrozoa	0.08	9.94	1.91	Predatory. mobile larvae (colonial, but with medusae phase).
Plumularia	0.09	3.47	0.07	Thecate hydroids growing as sediment attached, erect colonies. Filter feeders. Likely mobile larvae
Enoplea (spp.)	0.06	0.27	0	Nematodes. Many parasitic. Benthic and pelagic.
Pantopoda	0.07	0.04	0	Sea spiders. Carnivorous predators or scavengers. Benthic non-swimmers but with larvae stage
<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	0.09	2.23	0	European flat oyster. Filter feeders. Mobile larvae
Aiptasiidae	0.07	4.88	0	Sea anemones. Mainly predators. No free swimming medusae stage, not very mobile.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. a) Location of the benthic and pelagic ARMS in the southern Bay of Biscay. b) Photographic example of pelagic and benthic ARMS.

Figure 2. Photograph showing different colonization degree of benthic communities in benthic (left pannel, a-d) and pelagic (right pannel e-f) ARMS for Plate 1 and 8 at Top and Bottom faces. a) Top side of plate 1, b) Bottom side of plate 1, d) Top side of plate 8, d) Bottom side of plate 8. e-f) same for pelagic ARMS. In a) a community of brown algae (Phaeophyceae) can be appreciated, in contrast to b) where annelid worms Serpullidae dominate. In c) and d) a colony of bryozoans (Cheilostomatida) is shown. In pelagic ARMS, Serpullidae dominates the Bottom face of Plate 8 h) while in the other Plates (e-f-g) a combination of algae, bivalvia mollusks, barnacles and biofouling can be seen.

Figure 3. Stacked barplots displaying the percentage of (a-b) relative abundance in metabarcoding (number of reads) and (c-d) relative cover in photo-analysis of sessile and mobile taxonomic groups at phylum and class level across replicates of ARMS for each sampling site, size class and habitat.

Figure 4. a) ASVs richness in metabarcoding ARMS across sites, size classes, habitat, and traits in metabarcoding and b) species richness across sites, plate faces and habitat in photo-analysis. c) ASVs richness in metabarcoding ARMS for each site within size classes, trait and habitat, d) for each size within sites, traits, and habitats, for e) each habitat within sites and size classes, for f) each trait, within sites, sizes, and habitats. g) Species richness in photo-analysis ARMS across sites, within plate faces and habitat, for h) each plate face within sites and habitats, for i) each habitat within sites and plate faces. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles in the boxplots, and the band inside the box is the median. The whiskers extend up to 1.5-fold the interquartile range (Q3–Q1) from the box. The violin plot shows the kernel probability density of the data at different richness values.

F5. Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) showing the variability in the benthic cryptobiome composition based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrices of a)

metabarcoding and b) photo-analysis ARMS. Each color in the plot represents a different site, and each shape represent different size fractions in metabarcoding, and different plate faces in image analysis.

Figure 6. Community Dissimilarity matrices based on Bray-Curtis distances across a) sites and size classes for metabarcoding and b) across sites and plate faces for photo-analysis. A dissimilarity value of 1 indicates that the two sites, size classes or plate faces share no ASVs (metabarcoding) or species (photo-analysis) in common, while a value of 0 indicates the two sites, size classes or plate faces have identical communities.

Figure 7. ANalysis Of SIMilarity (ANOSIM) for metabarcoding ARMS including a) site, b) size, c) habitat and d) trait and for photo-analysis ARMS including e) site, g) habitat, h) plate number and i) plate face. The ANOSIM statistic “R” compares the mean of ranked dissimilarities between groups (for example sites) to the mean of ranked dissimilarities within groups (for example sites). An R value close to 1 suggests dissimilarity between groups while an R value close to 0 suggests an even distribution of high and low ranks within and between groups. The differences between groups were statistically tested using 1000 permutations. The boxplot shows variability of the ranked dissimilarities. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles. The band inside the box is the median. The jitter points add a small amount of random variation in dissimilarity ranks for each group.

Figure 8. Local Contribution to Beta Diversity (LCBD) describing the degree of uniqueness of each habitat and its contribution to the total variation in benthic composition for a) metabarcoding and b) photo-analysis ARMS. The boxplot shows variability of the LCBD for each habitat. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles. The band inside the box is the median. c) Number of unique and shared ASVs across pelagic and benthic habitats in metabarcoding ARMS.

F1

a)

b)

F2

F3

a

b

F4

F5

a

b

F6

a

b

c

d

F7

F8

c)

